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Co-doped zinc oxide by wide gap oxides: optical properties and photocatalytic activity

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Oksana Gorban^{1*}, *Igor Danilenko*¹, *Maria Guadalupe Mendez Medrano*², *Sergii. Gorban*¹, *Leonid Akhkozov*¹, *Olesya Shapovalova*³, *Tetyana Konstantinova*¹, *Svitlana Lyubchik*⁴

¹Materials science department, Donetsk institute for physics and engineering NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

*oxanag1@ukr.net

²École Polytechnique, Laboratoire de Physique des Interfaces et des Couches Minces, Paris, Île-de-France, France

³REQUIMTE, Associated Laboratory of Green Chemistry, Faculty of Science and Technology, University Nova de Lissboa, Caparica, Portugal

⁴NOVA ID FCT, Campus de Caparica, Caparica, Portugal

UV-visible spectroscopy is investigated the optical properties of wide band gap oxide doped zinc oxide. It was shown the introduction of these kinds of oxides (Al_2O_3 and/or ZrO_2) led to form of structural defects in zinc oxide matrix. These defects connect with the surface oxygen vacancies and lead to form a tail near absorption edge of these materials. It was shown that calcination temperature influence on the appearance defects in zinc oxide and as results on it photocatalytic activity to phenol degradation. The optical properties and photocatalytic activity (to phenol degradation) of Ag decorated materials was testing It was shown the decorated of these structure by Ag allows enhanced their antibacterial activity.

Introduction

Enhanced of photocatalytic properties of pure oxide systems is based on the building of forbidden band gap by introduction of cationic or/and anionic dopants in main oxide. Usually this approach use for enhanced of photosensitivity of materials to visible range of irradiation spectrum [1]. Also this approach allows to introduce in catalytic systems the ions with variable valence that creation the additional centers with oxidative characters. The wide spectrum of cationic dopant uses for building of such catalytic structures. In review [2] the main kinds of cationic dopants to ZnO are shown, there are oxides of different elements (Ag, Al, Mg, Bi, Cd, Fe, Sn etc). However the comparison of photocatalytic activity for enhanced oxide by different dopant is very difficult because the many parameters which influence on catalytic activity is changed and different kinds of organic pollutants was used for estimation of efficiency of complex catalysts. In set of work the multicomponent oxide systems were synthesized [3]. It may be as only cationic dopants or only anionic dopants [4] and also the cationic and anionic dopants together (for example, Fe,N co-doped oxides [5]).

It is noted that the most of investigators work on TiO_2 systems although it has cost that is more expensive than zinc oxide which has similar or something higher catalytic activity. It connected with less stability of zinc oxide in water, high sensitivity to photocorrosion and fast electron-hole

recombination [6]. In this connection ZnO oxide may be modified by wide band gap semiconductors such as ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3 or MgO which show the high stability to degradation of material under irradiation. The some authors noted that the Zr-doping of zinc oxide leads to possibly change the recombination of electron – holes pairs because the Zr atoms give a deep energy levels in forbidden band gap of zinc oxide [7]. It is may give a high hole activity of modified materials. However, the creation of heterojunction between different oxides of complex structure change the structure and surface state of each component of oxide heterostructure. The wide band gap oxides also may be rich the cations of other composite components and such as the different types of defects in cationic and anionic sublattice may be created. It may lead to creation photosensitive of wide band gap oxide components to irradiation in near UV irradiation [8].

Such as the analysis of reviews of last years show the tendency of using of complex composite systems and the accent to using of more cheaper of ZnO than TiO_2 and the solving of problem its stability together with enhanced of their catalytic activity.

Experimental

Doped wide band oxides zinc oxide nanoparticles (NPs) were synthesized using a precipitation technique from determined salts in oxalate solution. All used chemicals were of

chemical purity. The sediments were washed several times with distilled water before drying in a microwave furnace ($P = 700 \text{ W}$, $f = 2.45 \text{ GHz}$). The dried precipitates were calcined in a resistive furnace at 400, 500, 700 °C with a dwell time of 2 h. The amount of doped oxides (ZrO_2 , Al_2O_3 or ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 together) is 0.1 and 10 mol. %.

The optical properties of ZnO nanopowders were measured on a Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer with Internal Diffuse Reflectance sphere (Agilent Technologies, USA). Kinetic of degradation was estimated by UV spectroscopy and liquid chromatography HPLC. ESR spectra was obtained on CSM 8400 spectrometers (9.45 GHz)

Results and discussion

Fig.1 show the UV spectra of wide gap oxide doped zinc oxide that was obtained at different calcination temperature.

Fig.1 UV spectra of wide gap oxide doped zinc oxide a) 500°C, b) 700°C.

According to presented date the introduction of band gap oxide leads to shift band gap position in side of less energies (red shift). The values of band

gap energies of these systems are given in tabl.1.

Table 1 Band gap energies of wide band doped ZnO

Oxide type	Band gap energy, eV	
	500°C	700°C
ZnO	3.16	3.19
ZnO-0.1 Al ₂ O ₃	3.13	3.09
ZnO-0.1 Al ₂ O ₃ -0.1ZrO ₂	3.13	3.11

Introduction wide gap dopants in zinc oxide lead to appearance of the tail in optical spectra of complex oxides. The presence of tail near absorption edge marks on defects in zinc oxide structure. It is noted that the system co-doped Al_2O_3 has more high tail level than other presented systems. The increasing of calcination temperature led to decrease defects in structure of pure zinc oxide and tails become less pronounced for co-doped systems.

Fig. 2 shows UV spectra of phenol solution after UV irradiation in presence of investigated systems.

Fig.2 UV spectra of phenol solution after determined time of UV irradiation in presence of investigated systems with $T_{\text{calc}}=500^\circ\text{C}$ a) ZnO, b) ZnO-0.1% Al_2O_3 , c) ZnO-0.1% ZrO_2 -0.1% Al_2O_3

The decreasing of absorption peak at 270 nm shows the decreasing of phenol concentration, but the increasing of peak at 278 nm shows the accumulation of pyrocatechol, the peaks at 244 and 293 nm shows on producing of hydroquinone in reaction of phenol degradation. The co-doped zinc oxide by wide band gap oxides did not change the process of phenol degradation under UV

irradiation (354 nm).

Fig. 3 shows the kinetic of phenol degradation according to HPLC data of ZnO-0.1% ZrO₂-0.1% Al₂O₃ that was obtained with different calcination temperature.

Fig.3 Kinetic of phenol degradation according to HPLC data in presence of ZnO-0.1% ZrO₂-0.1% Al₂O₃ that was obtained with different calcination temperature.

As we can see the growth of calcination temperature led to decreasing of photocatalytic activity of doped zinc. It is connected with noted above the decreasing of defects of structures at growth calcination temperature (decreasing of tail at absorption edge is evidence).

Enhanced the photoactivity of such materials may be realized at decorated of it by Ag. As example in fig. 4 show the optical spectra of Ag decorated ZnO. For these causes the temperature is not critical. These materials shown a high antibacterial activity in testing.

Fig. 4 Kinetic of phenol degradation (HPLC data) in presence Ag decorated ZnO (Tcalc=500 and 700°C)

ESR spectrum of ZnO-0.1%ZrO₂-1%Ag₂O shows the wide signal with $g=2.039$ that corresponds to surface small Ag clusters and isotropic signal at $g=1.959$ which corresponds to defects which connects with oxygen vacancies in ZnO. It is noted that for ZnO-0.1%Al₂O₃-1%Ag₂O in ESR spectrum only isotropic signal at $g=1.959$ is observed and their intensity is bigger than for first system.

Conclusion

These results show that the ZnO doped by wide band gap oxides may be used as creation of defects in ZnO structure which do these materials more sensitive to sun light and which shows a high photocatalytic activity to phenol degradation. The possible mechanism of phenol degradation under UV irradiation in presence of co-doped ZnO by wide band gap oxides (Al₂O₃ and ZrO₂) is discussed. The influence of calcination temperature on optical properties and photoactivity is discussed.

Keywords: Zinc oxide, band gap, dopants, optical properties, photocatalytic activity

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